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DEVELOPING THE PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF FUTURE FINE ART TEACHERS IN THE PROCESS OF PRACTICAL TRAINING

Annotation: *The article is devoted to the development of visual skills by teaching the rules of practical training in professional disciplines in the professional training of future teachers of fine arts. Drawing short sketches of nature and imagination based on nature in the formation of students' competencies in practical classes, which is the basis for the development of students' ability to quickly see and understand nature.*

Key words: *sketch drawing, practical exercises, fine arts, pencil drawing, composition, fine arts, nature, perception,.*

Practical exercises are the main criterion in the training of future specialists in the fine arts. The main of them are practical exercises in the field of drawing, and in the educational process, practical work is carried out in stages by the method of depiction "From general to specific and from specific to general", which is one of the foundations of fine arts.

It is designed to give students a brief sketch of its characteristics, depending on the nature, in the formation of their competencies in practical training. It is also designed to help students develop the ability to see and understand nature quickly.

Observation, perception, and sketching often occur at the same time. To improve your drawing skills in practice, it is important to identify the following six types of techniques used to draw sketches.

- Sketches of nature, performed directly from beginning to end, observing nature.
- Sketches depicted in combination (first by nature, then by nature - by memory).
- Sketches that are made only from memory, that is, after some time after observation, when the ability to see in the mind is strengthened.
- Sketches of imaginations related to the ability to revive perceptions of certain objects, living objects, and surrounding events that were previously perceived in the human mind.
- Sketches made in a complex way, that is, using all of the above methods, including imaginary methods.
- Imagination - drawing a generalized sketch of an image based on any creative idea or artistic image, subject, plot, etc., reviving their ideas about objects and events.

In practice, when sketching, the condition, number, and complexity of the object being depicted at the same time (at rest or in motion) are, in other words, the context

in which the sketch is drawn, as well as the objective conditions encountered in practice.

One of these conditions is whether or not time is limited for nature observation and sketch execution. This, in turn, depends on the immobility of nature or the degree of excitation (speed of movement). In other words, the method of sketching is influenced by two factors: time and the state of nature.

In addition to these interrelated factors, the performer and his ability to work (hence the character and quality of the image in the sketch) are also affected by external objective conditions to which the painter must adapt (rural, mountain, urban landscapes and so on.

Drawing a sketch of nature can only be done from beginning to end under one condition, that is, when nature is completely motionless.

This nature can be, first of all, inanimate objects (for example, fruits, flowers, trees, rocks, and some types of landscapes.

The artist's work is relatively calm, as the aim of the sketch is to depict an incomplete generalized view of nature. If the goal has been achieved and nature is not yet moving, then it is possible to move from the sketch to the line (plate). In addition to the edges of the paper, you can make more detailed lines of some pieces.

If the immobility of nature is conditional and accidental, in some cases it is temporary, that is, nature at any time, at a time unknown to the painter, changes his position, facial expressions, gestures if it changes and even disappears altogether from the point of view, then the nature of the work in drawing a sketch from nature will change drastically. This can happen when you accidentally draw a sketch of a live model (sitting in a park bench or getting up, or suddenly lying down quietly, etc.).

When making a sketch (or drawing) of a landscape - you don't have to make sure that the weather or lighting conditions don't change, the wind can stop, the flat water surface can be shaken by waves, and the sky can suddenly be covered with black clouds).

In nature, living things are not as rhythmic as in an artist's workshop or as a classroom attribute. It lasts a lifetime, and its natural, temporary immobility can be immediate, and sometimes unexpected.

It should be noted that such immovable conditions of a living model, that is, a calm, serene appearance, are the most valuable for the observer's eyes. On the contrary, a living model that stands out in the same situation always loses its expressiveness, because in any case, there is artificiality. Plus, the look on your face will eventually get tired, which will affect your character.

Therefore, the artist must always be ready to accurately depict a living model in a sketch.

You need to make the most of every minute, even every second, to observe and sketch the time you have to work. It is no coincidence that the word "sketch" has such meanings as "short", "very fast", "at a glance", "lightning speed", "instantaneous".

The purpose of sketching is to instantly display the results of observations on paper. Of course, if there is enough time, then it is not even a sketch.

In the classroom, especially in the early stages of sketching, students always have enough time to observe and describe.

But outside of the auditorium, working on a sketch can be abruptly interrupted, both when observing and drawing at the same time. Sometimes an artist tries to achieve a goal as quickly as possible, to immediately reflect the typical and characteristic features of nature. The tracking time corresponds to the execution time. In this case, with the perception of nature, the performance becomes sharper. That is, without distraction, without giving in to small, secondary details, one immediately tries to grasp the essential aspects of the subject, using the simplest means to a minimum.

First of all, with a few reliable lines, it is necessary to determine the location and size of the future image - its outline (construction). That is why it is necessary to take down the whole mass of nature, taking into account the main parts, and their movements.

When you start drawing a sketch, it seems to stop for a while, but if you follow the logic of the work, everything will fall into place. If nature maintains its immutability, it is necessary to immediately begin to elaborate on the identified ideas, to quickly grasp the most basic, characteristic features.

As nature begins to move, as it changes its position, you have to use your ability to see from memory to complete this sketch.

Advanced vision (memory) is a great way to fill in the details of what you have seen before.

A sketch that starts with nature and then ends in memory without his participation is considered "Combined".

The reduction in observation time also complicates the work on the sketch and requires more memory. This is very common in practice.

It is very difficult to capture in a moment the state of nature, which is in constant motion. In that case, it's important to catch the glimpse of it all at once and immediately, without delay, write down what is stamped in your memory. That way, the sealed image will not lose its "freshness". An example of this is an athlete who is running fast in front of you. Achieving such a task is possible in practice. To do this, you need to be able to quickly perceive the expression of the movement at a glance (for example, the body of the running athlete, the movement of the legs, head and arms). But here we must not forget to put together the rough lines, that is, to coordinate the composition. 3

If the visual acuity is strong, it is possible to generalize the images, which are very short, and sometimes even in a second, imprinted in memory. A sketch made in this way is like a memory stamped on paper.

Corrections and additions to such sketches can only be made by repeating the athlete's actions (almost the same action).

The need to work on a sketch based solely on visual memory arises only in situations where external conditions allow observation. For example, a portrait of a passenger sitting in front of you in a vehicle looks like the character of the picture you are imagining, and the image you have been looking for for a long time comes out in front of you. It is impossible to draw it from nature, because it can divert its gaze, turn its head or change its appearance, and so on.

You have to choose a way to solve the tasks set before you, to use your eyesight: to observe and study your nature without noticing it, to distinguish its characteristic features (especially its distinctive features). you try to remember. The passenger dropped off at the station. Immediately, without delay, take your pocket album (otherwise it may fade from your memory) and draw a sketch from the memory, just as you remember the situation of that passenger.

There are many such examples. But in order for an artist to develop visual memory, he needs to draw sketches of the person in motion, especially a group of people with different personalities and speeds of movement. For example, drawing sketches for athletes in sports such as handball, football, athletics, gymnastics, and volleyball can be a great way for a student to develop skills such as plastic anatomy and line drawing.

It should be borne in mind that the quality of the image to be remembered as a result of observation and its imprinting in memory are influenced by many factors and circumstances. In particular, in some cases, what is studied in the process of direct imagery, carefully observing the schematic drawing of nature on paper, is well remembered. Anything that can be mechanically copied without analyzing the image will usually not be remembered for long.

Imaginary sketching is not about observing nature directly. It is performed only on the basis of previously perceived events in the world of the subject and in the mind. Imagination is more general than perception. They have less detail and only reflect the basic features of the object and the event. That is why an imaginary sketch is so close to the phrase "out of itself" that it is said to depict an object or event with additions and additions to some aspects of it. It is different from a sketch drawn directly on nature.

In the imagination, the artist is free from factors such as time and nature. He should be calm and focus on his sketches, drawing sketches. It is also important to ensure that the image is realized in a realistic way.

The simplest task is to be able to imagine a simple chair on the floor, to remember the shape of the chair, its construction and the ratio of the basic dimensions, and to imagine its imaginary practical state.

So what does this same chair look like from above and below? The answer to a self-question is a challenge at first, and you need to overcome it before you can pick up a pen and start drawing. The more complex the shape of an object, the more difficult it is to imagine it.

The painter is faced with the task of restoring in his mind (imagination) a wide-ranging image of the object. Such a restoration process is of synthetic significance and includes not only the idea of the shape of the object, but also its latitude, other dimensions such as its structure, its relative size, proportions, direction and speed of motion.

For example, if we draw a sketch of a complex living form, such as a human figure, without nature, and generalize it, then our imaginary nature will move in a fast motion, turn, or in another position (say, over an obstacle with an anchor). the task is much more complicated.

Before performing a sketch, we need to imagine the image in memory, its structure, and, in general, what size this shape will take on paper from a certain point of view. Only then, after calling out the plastic anatomy of man for help in memory, "taking out" a sheet of paper on a piece of paper, on top of that, the ratio of torso, head, limbs, their size, shortening during movement you can start drawing the proportions, taking into account the state of illumination.

The above examples are not in vain. The first example shows the simplest way to draw a sketch in the imagination. If we compare it with the method of sketching from nature, which is based on continuous active display and analysis of the depicted form, it is clear that the sketch drawn in the imagination is based on the restoration of a previously known and memorized form.

Exercises made from complex parts of the human body, such as the bones of the head, arms, and soles of the feet, also work well.

The ability to freely and expressively depict the human body in any position and fast-moving "without itself" (without nature) and more as a result of exercise. Training sketches made in the imagination have a great influence on the completion of the skills of depicting a person in different situations, that is, in motionless and moving states.

In order to gain a deeper understanding of the human body in practice, it is enough to analyze many of the paintings by famous artists in history and to look carefully at the appearance of human figures. They are all imaginary drawings.

Much attention is paid to auxiliary exercises to test the mastery of the material covered in the ongoing learning tasks to teach practical drawing in the imagination.

Such imaginative sketches and drawing tests help students develop important skills in drawing with confidence. In particular, it has a positive effect on the

development of descriptive competencies through practical exercises in the performance of tasks with a clear purpose.

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